

The causes of word borrowings in languages

Rakhimova Guzal Yuldashovna, Associate Professor , Department of Translation Theory and Practice, Urgench State University ,Uzbekistan
Bakhtiyarova Gulasal, 2-year student, Department of Translation Theory and Practice,Urgench State University

Annotation: This article is about the placement of a newly introduced word, its ability to convey the basic needs of the people hearing it, and the internal capabilities of the coordinating language. We analyzed about determining whether it changes completely or is only used once before disappearing.

Key words: borrowed words, assimilation, migration, equivalent, destiny, civilization.

Introduction

Among the languages of the world, there is not a single language that does not contain more or less borrowed words or "is not mixed to a certain extent". The total number of world languages is not small. Currently, there are more than 2000 languages. Each of these languages has its own history, destiny, place and position in the life of society. In addition, they have characteristics and characteristics such as interaction, cooperation, acceptance of words from each other and assimilation. These issues are, in particular, for what reasons a word in the vocabulary of one language is transferred to another language, how does it get absorbed into the vocabulary of the receiving language? - such questions have been of interest to linguists and have been sufficiently answered in a number of scientific-general theoretical and practical works . Based on these works, we name the main reasons of borrowings.

If we look into the distant past, we can see that foreign words were mainly transferred to other languages through oral communication (because there was no writing). Verbal communication took place in close proximity, when peoples moved from one place to another (migration), in trade and commerce, or at least when they waged wars with each other. If these characterize one side of the nature of the reasons for the origin of the word, on the other hand, they also depend on the spirit

of the people. Because "compared to a person's hand and eye, his ear and tongue are faster and more active" [9; 6].

Literature Review and materials

Today's social life and production growth, civilization and scientific-technical, informational-technological development are rapidly penetrating every corner of the world, completely destroying the opportunities for peoples and languages to live separately from each other. In addition, there is not a single nation on earth that, during its development, ignores the successes of the nations of the outside world and does not learn from them. Naturally, all of these are first of all reflected in language and through language. According to the calculations of linguists, there are more than 7,000 borrowed words in the Latin language (now considered dead), several tens of thousands in the German language, more than half of the English language, and more than 10 percent of the Russian language. Regarding the Uzbek language, F. Abdullayev cited the following facts: "The results of statistical calculations carried out by different authors for different periods (between 1920-1970) regarding the lexicon of the Uzbek literary language" -showed the gradual growth of the international lexicon and, in particular, the gradual quantitative decrease of the number of words taken from the Arabic language [10; 5].

If we dwell on the specific reasons for word acquisition, first of all, we must say that in order for one language to acquire a word from another language, the word that is being acquired is not in the receiving language, it is The main factor is that it means and expresses what is necessary and related to vital needs in that language. For these cases, it is usually characteristic of things, objects, events and concepts adopted from a foreign language and their names. In such situations, the receiving language tends to be very economical, therefore, it assimilates the incoming news as much as possible in one word. The new thing, phenomenon or new concept is accepted as it is without giving an explanation in the local language. For example, computer, container, football, smartphone, internet, etc.

Main part:Analyses and results

Geographical terms, socio-political words, words of the language owners that mean national, non-existent and unusual things and events are among the obvious reasons for word acquisition. Because when we interact with the natives of this language, we can avoid these words, without them our thoughts cannot be expressed.

For example, labor, trade unions, Newfoundland, Bundestag, business, college, firm, etc.

The fact that the word is a synonym (equivalent) of the word being learned in the language being learned and its parallel use is also an objective process. For example, accountant - accountant, airliner - plane, sniper - marksman, handball - handball, etc. But this does not mean that these appropriations have the same denotation. They differ from each other in their relative meaning, place of use and purpose. Basically, according to these differences, they are distinguished.

The meaning of some acquisitions requires another adjective in the target language. This excess often leads to the use of appropriation itself. For example, a rally is a large gathering, a broiler is a broiler, and so on.

In order to give the basic meaning of most of the adjectives, it is necessary to make phrases or whole sentences. In such cases, it is better to use the word itself, for example, a sandwich - a piece of bread with a piece of cheese or sausage spread on it; goal - mainly in football, the introduction of the ball into the goal of the opposing team.

In addition, the semantic changes of the meanings of the acquired words in the receiving language, that is, their obvious manifestation or generalization of their meanings, narrowing or expanding of the meaning, acquiring a negative or positive meaning. , a polysemic word becomes monosemic or vice versa, a monosemic word becomes polysemic, there are a number of aspects such as being used to increase the variety of speech, which are also objective reasons for word acquisition.

It is impossible not to include the mass media, which is currently considered the most important source, among the above-mentioned reasons for word appropriation. The reason for this is the fact that there are many information bureaus, TV channels in all countries of the world, and of course, the information distributed through the Internet is distributed in almost all languages of the countries. Information agencies and websites in each country should reprocess the messages from these sources in the language of that country and deliver them to the people as soon as possible. These media also carry out word acquisition in three different ways: 1) without change, that is, by itself; 2) literally translated; 3) mixed.

The fate of newly introduced words, i.e., whether they change completely or whether they are uttered once and disappear, depends on the position of this word, its power to express the vital and daily needs of the people receiving the word, and,

moreover, It depends on the internal capabilities of the coordinating language. The analysis of these requires, first of all, to dwell on the issue of word acquisition and acquisitions.

Used Literature

1. O'zbek tili leksikologiyasi. Toshkent, 1981, 78-82 –betlar.
2. Боровков А. К. Таджико-Узбекское двуязычие и вопросы взаимодействия таджикского и узбекского языков. Ученые записки Института востоковедения. Т. IV. М., 1952, с. 188
3. SulanB. Zu einigen Fragen des Bilinguismus. – “Slavica”, 1963, Seite die Seite 14.
4. Heller K. Das Fremdwort in der deutschen Sprache der Gegenwart. Leipzig, 1966, S, 7.
5. Shoabdurahmonov Sh. O'zbekistonda tilshunoslikni rivojlantirishning aktual problemalari. –“O'zbek tili va adabiyoti”, 1982, 5-son, 4-bet.
6. Боровков А. К. Ko'rsatilgan asar, 10-bet.
7. Seiler A. Entwicklung der deutschen Kultur im Spiegel des deutschen Lehnwortes. 4. Teil, Halle/Saale, 1925, S. 7.
8. Микитич Л.Д. Иноязычная лексика. Л., 1967; Крыин Л.П. О причинах лексического заимствования. –«Русский язык в школе», 1965, №3.
9. Seiler A. Ko'rsatilgan asar, 6-bet.
10. Abdullayev F.A. Rus tilining o'zbek adabiy tiliga ko'rsatgan ta'sir doirasi haqida. – “O'zbek tili va adabiyoti”, 1980, 3-son, 5-bet.
11. O'zbek tili leksikologiyasi. Toshkent, 1981, 83 – 84-betlar.
12. Stepanova M.D., Cernyševa I.I. Lexikologie der deutschen Gegenwartssprache. Moskau, 1975, S. 47.
13. Сулейманова Н. К. ГЁТЕ И ЕГО ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯ КАК ШЕДЕВР МИРОВОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ //ИЗВОДКОР О'QITUVCHI. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 29. – С. 343-346.
14. Рахимова Г. Ю. ФОРМАЛЬНАЯ СТРУКТУРА АНГЛИЙСКИХ РЕДУПЛИКАТИВНЫХ СЛОВ //ВОСТОЧНО ЕВРОПЕЙСКИЙ НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ. – 2020. – Т. 57. – №. part 6. – С. 48.
15. Рахимова Г. Ю. ФОРМАЛЬНАЯ СТРУКТУРА АНГЛИЙСКИХ РЕДУПЛИКАТИВНЫХ СЛОВ //Wschodnioeuropejskie Czasopismo Naukowe. – 2020. – №. 5-6. – С. 48-50.

16. Рахимова Г. Ю., Жуматов Р. Я., Норбоев У. Система номинативных единиц современного английского языка //The Seventh European Conference on Languages, Literature and Linguistics. – 2015. – С. 21-26.
17. Рахимова Г. Ю., Якубова З. Ш. СИСТЕМА НОМИНАТИВНЫХ ЕДИНИЦ СОВРЕМЕННОГО АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА //Евразийский союз ученых. – 2020. – №. 7-3. – С. 14-17.
18. Рахимова Г. Ю., Якубова З. Ш. Система номинативных единиц современного английского языка //Евразийский Союз Ученых. – 2020. – №. 7-3 (76). – С. 14-17.
19. Oktambaevna P. N. Periodic functional study of military terms in our national language //Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 139-144.
20. Oktambaevna P. N. Periodic functional study of military terms in our national language //Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 139-144.
21. Surayyo I. et al. PRAGMALINGUISTIC FEATURES OF TEXT AND LANGUAGE ADVERTISING //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 15. – С. 75-77.
22. Сулейманова Н. К. ГЁТЕ И ЕГО ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯ КАК ШЕДЕВР МИРОВОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ //PJODKOR O'QITUVCHI. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 29. – С. 343-346.
23. Сулейманова Н. К. ДИАЛОГ КУЛЬТУР ЗАПАДА И ВОСТОКА КАК ОСНОВА ЦЕЛОСТНОГО МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЯ //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 18. – С. 1362-1364.
24. Shavkatovna A. N. et al. DIFFICULTIES STUDENTS FACE WHILE LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN UZBEK SCHOOLS //TADQIQOTLAR. – 2023. – Т. 28. – №. 1. – С. 81-83.
25. Litvinenko E. V. et al. Phono-morpho-lexical similarity of auxiliary morphemes of the dictionary «mukaddimat al-adab»(Xii-century) az-zamakhshari with kazakh language //Utopía y Praxis Latinoamericana. – 2020. – Т. 25. – №. 12. – С. 302-308.

26. Yuldashovna R. G. et al. Linguistic Considerations on the Functional Semantics of English Reduplicative Elements //Remittances Review. – 2023. – T. 8. – №. 4.
27. Yuldashovna R. G. The Semantic Structure of a Compound Word in Languages //Remittances Review. – 2023. – T. 8. – №. 4.
28. Yuldashovna R. G. The Semantic Structure of a Compound Word in Languages //Remittances Review. – 2023. – T. 8. – №. 4.
29. Farkhodovna M. R., Yuldashovna R. G. AN ANTHROPOCENTRIC APPROACH TO TERMS AND LANGUAGE //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2023. – T. 12. – №. 06. – C. 25-27.
30. Farkhodovna M. R., Yuldashovna R. G. AN ANTHROPOCENTRIC APPROACH TO TERMS AND LANGUAGE //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2023. – T. 12. – №. 06. – C. 25-27.
31. Yuldashovna R. G. Analyses of reduplicative words in English language //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – C. 44-48.
32. Yuldashovna R. G. Analyses of reduplicative words in English language //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – C. 44-48.
33. Yuldashovna R. G., Kudratovna B. D. The scientific features of simultaneous translation (conference translation) and the current role in the process of translation //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 04. – C. 49-52.
34. Yuldashovna R. G., Kudratovna B. D. The scientific features of simultaneous translation (conference translation) and the current role in the process of translation //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 04. – C. 49-52.

35. Рахимова Г. Ю., Арнамуратов Э. Структурно-семантические особенности и коммуникативные функции редупликативных слов в английском языке //Архивариус. – 2020. – №. 5 (50). – С. 39-42.
36. Рахимова Г. Ю., Арнамуратов Э. СТРУКТУРНО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ И КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЕ ФУНКЦИИ РЕДУПЛИКАТИВНЫХ СЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ //Контактная информация организационного комитета конференции. – С. 39.
37. Рахимова Г. Ю., Арнамуратов Э. СТРУКТУРНО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ И КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЕ ФУНКЦИИ РЕДУПЛИКАТИВНЫХ СЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ //Архивариус. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 39-42.
38. Masharipovna S. G., Matnazarovna P. M., Toxirovna E. Y. VOCABULARY TEACHING STRATEGIES USING IN ESP CLASSES //Кронос: общественные науки. – 2019. – №. 2 (16). – С. 17-18.
39. Yesmurzaeva A. THE ACT OF ORAL COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 89-91.
40. Ibragimova X. S., Saparbaeva G. M. OG ‘ZAKI MULOQOT AKTIDA OBYEKTIV VA SUBYEKTIV MODALLIK KATEGORIYALARI //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 102-105.
41. Saparbaeva G., Jumaniyazova S. THE INTERNET IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. B5. – С. 62-66.
42. Saparbaeva G. M., Azatova N. A. TRANSLATION STRATEGIES OF CULTURE-SPECIFIC WORD INFAIRYTALES FROM AND INTO THE UZBEK LANGUAGE //Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
43. Saparbaeva G. M. et al. THE MAIN THEORETICAL PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF CULTURE SPECIFIC CONCEPT //Студенческий вестник. – 2021. – №. 4-7. – С. 44-47.
44. Saparbayeva G. M. et al. THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THESAURUS RELATIONSHIP IN ARTISTIC TEXTS //Интернаука. – 2019. – №. 23-4. – С. 30-31.

45. Saparbayeva G. M. et al. COMPARING THE ANALYSIS OF METAPHORS BOTH IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES BASED ON THE NOVEL “SISTER CARRIE” BY THEODORE DREISER //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF HISTORY, CULTURAL STUDIES AND PHILOLOGY. – 2019. – С. 71-77.
46. Saparbayeva G. M. et al. TEACHING ENGLISH FOR TOURISM //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF HISTORY, CULTURAL STUDIES AND PHILOLOGY. – 2019. – С. 78-82.
47. Saparbayeva G. M., Jamolatdinova L. R., Bobojonova Y. I. THE PECULARITIES OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF HISTORY, CULTURAL STUDIES AND PHILOLOGY. – 2019. – С. 64-70.
48. Saparbayeva G. M., Abdullaeva N. F., Bobozhonova Y. I. THE ROLE OF ENGLISH IN TRAVELLING //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 17. – С. 59-63.
49. Saparbaeva G. M., Pirnazarova M. M., Egamberganova Y. T. VOCABULARY TEACHING STRATEGIES USING IN ESP CLASSES //Chronos: общественные науки. – 2019. – №. 2. – С. 18-20.
50. Saparbayeva G. M., Abdullaeva N. F., Bobozhonova Y. I. THE ROLE OF ENGLISH IN TRAVELLING //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 17. – С. 59-63.
51. Masharipovna S. G., Farhodovna A. N., Igorovna B. Y. The role of English in travelling //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 17 (64). – С. 59-63.
52. Saparbayeva G., Ibragimova A. Combining digital stories with the Internet //Бюллетень науки и практики. – 2018. – Т. 4. – №. 7. – С. 503-505.
53. Gulandom S., Anahon I. Combining digital stories with the internet //Бюллетень науки и практики. – 2018. – Т. 4. – №. 7. – С. 503-505.
54. Anahon I., Gulamand S. Methods and techniques to integrate digital stories in ELT //Бюллетень науки и практики. – 2018. – Т. 4. – №. 5. – С. 681-688.
55. Saparbaeva G. M., Matyakubov Z. M., Dusmetova S. M. Semantic analysis of words denoting ‘motherland’ in english sayings and proverbs //Бакалавр. – 2016. – №. 7-8. – С. 20-25.

56. Tillayevna M. G., Alisherovna O. D., Masharipovna S. G. Social and Linguistic peculiarities of Taboo //European journal of literature and linguistics. – 2016. – №. 2. – C. 23-24.

57. Jumaniyazovich J. A., Masharipovna S. G., Rustamovna S. B. Sanscrit borrowings in English and Uzbek languages //The Seventh European Conference on Languages, Literature and Linguistics. – 2015. – C. 26.

58. Feruza B. NEYROLINGVISTIKA TILSHUNOSLIKNING YANGI SOHALARIDAN BIRI //PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 52-55.

Research Science and
Innovation House

